

ARTICLE

Strong Insertion of a Contra-Continuous Function Between two Comparable Contra- α -Continuous (Contra-C-Continuous) Functions

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Received : January 10, 2020; Accepted : January 15, 2020; Published : January 21, 2020.

Abstract

Necessary and sufficient conditions in terms of lower cut sets are given to the strong insertion of a contra-continuous function between two comparable real-valued functions on such topological spaces that kernel of sets is open.

Key words: Insertion, Strong binary relation, C-open set, Semi-preopen set, α -open set, Contra-continuous function, Lower cut set

Introduction

The concept of a C-open set in a topological space was introduced by E. Hatir, T. Noiri and S. Yksel in [12]. The authors define a set S to be a C-open set if $S = U \cap A$, where U is open and A is semi-preclosed. A set S is a C-closed set if its complement (denoted by S^c) is a C-open set or equivalently, if $S = U \cup A$, where U is closed and A is semi-preopen. The authors show that a subset of a topological space is open if and only if it is an α -open set and a C-open set or equivalently a subset of a topological space is closed if and only if it is an α -closed set and a C-closed set. This enables them to provide the following decomposition of continuity: a function is continuous if and only if it is α -continuous and C-continuous or equivalently a function is contra-continuous if and only if it is contra α -continuous and contra-C-continuous.

Recall that a subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called α -open if A is the difference of an open and a nowhere dense subset of X . A set A is called α -closed if its complement is α -open or equivalently if A is the union of a closed and a nowhere dense set. Sets which are dense in some regular closed subspace are called semi-preopen or β -open. A set is semi-preclosed or β -closed if its complement is semi-preopen or β -open.

In [6] it was shown that a set A is β -open if and only if $A \subseteq \text{Cl}(\text{Int}(\text{Cl}(A)))$. A generalized class of closed sets was considered by Maki in [19]. He investigated the sets that can be represented as the union of closed sets and called them V -sets. Complements of V -sets, i.e., sets that are intersection of open sets are called \wedge -sets

[19].

Recall that a real-valued function f defined on a topological space X is called A -continuous [23] if the preimage of every open subset of \mathbb{R} belongs to A , where A is a collection of subsets of X . Most of the definitions of function used throughout this paper are consequences of the definition of A -continuity. However, for unknown concepts the reader may refer to [4, 11]. In the recent literature many topologists had focused their research in the direction of investigating different types of generalized continuity.

J. Dontchev in [5] introduced a new class of mappings called contra continuity. S. Jafari and T. Noiri in [13, 14] exhibited and studied among others a new weaker form of this class of mappings called contra- α -continuous. A good number of researchers have also initiated different types of contracontinuous like mappings in the papers [1, 3, 8, 9, 10, 22].

Hence, a real-valued function f defined on a topological space X is called contra-continuous (resp. contra C-continuous, contra- α -continuous) if the preimage of every open subset of \mathbb{R} is closed (resp. C-closed, α -closed) in X [5].

Results of Kat $\check{\text{e}}\text{tov}$ [15, 16] concerning binary relations and the concept of an indefinite lower cut set for a real valued function, which is due to Brooks [2], are used in order to give a necessary and sufficient condition for the insertion of a contra-continuous function between two comparable real valued functions on such topological spaces that \wedge -sets or kernel of sets are open [19].

If g and f are real-valued functions defined on a space X , we write g

$\leq f$ in case $g(x) \leq f(x)$ for all x in X .

The following definitions are modifications of the conditions considered in [17].

A property P defined relative to a real-valued function on a topological space is a cc -property provided that any constant function has property P and provided that the sum of a function with property P and any contra continuous function also has property P . If $P1$ and $P2$ are cc -properties, the following terminology is used:

- A space X has the weak cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$ if and only if for any functions g and f on X such that $g \leq f$, g has property $P1$ and f has property $P2$, then there exists a contra continuous function h such that $g \leq h \leq f$.
- A space X has the strong cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$ if and only if for any functions g and f on X such that $g \leq f$, g has property $P1$ and f has property $P2$, then there exists a contra-continuous function h such that $g \leq h \leq f$ and if $g(x) < f(x)$ for any x in X , then $g(x) < h(x) < f(x)$.

In this paper, for a topological space whose \wedge -sets or kernel of the sets are open, gives a sufficient condition for the weak cc -insertion property. Also for a space with the weak cc -insertion property, we give necessary and sufficient conditions for the space to have the strong cc -insertion property. Several insertion theorems are obtained as corollaries from these results.

Results

Before giving a sufficient condition for insertability of a contra-continuous function, the necessary definitions and terminology are stated.

The abbreviation cc , $c\alpha c$ and cCc are used for contra-continuous, contra α -continuous and contra- C -continuous, respectively.

Definition 1. Let A be a subset of a topological space (X, τ) . We define the subsets A^\wedge and A^\vee as follows:

$$A^\wedge = \cap \{0 : 0 \supseteq A, 0 \in (X, \tau)\} \text{ and } A^\vee = \cup \{F : F \subseteq A, F^c \subseteq (X, \tau)\}$$

In [7, 18, 21], A^\wedge is called the kernel of A . The family of all α -open, α -closed, C -open and C -closed will be denoted by $\alpha O(X, \tau)$, $\alpha C(X, \tau)$, $CO(X, \tau)$ and $CC(X, \tau)$, respectively. We define the subsets $\alpha(A^\wedge)$, $\alpha(A^\vee)$, $C(A^\wedge)$ and $C(A^\vee)$ as follows:

$$\alpha(A^\wedge) = \cap \{0 : 0 \supseteq A, 0 \in \alpha(X, \tau)\},$$

$$\alpha(A^\vee) = \cup \{F : F \subseteq A, F \in \alpha C(X, \tau)\},$$

$$C(A^\wedge) = \cap \{0 : 0 \supseteq A, 0 \in C O(X, \tau)\} \text{ and}$$

$$C(A^\vee) = \cup \{F : F \subseteq A, F \in CC(X, \tau)\} . \alpha(A^\wedge) \text{ (resp. } C(A^\wedge))$$

is called the α -kernel (resp. C -kernel) of A . The following first two definitions are modifications of conditions considered in [15, 16].

Definition 2. If ρ is a binary relation in a set S then ρ^- is defined as follows: $x \rho^- y$ if and only if $y \rho v$ implies $x \rho v$ and $u \rho x$ implies $u \rho y$ for any u and v in S .

Definition 3. A binary relation ρ in the power set $P(X)$ of a topological space X is called a strong binary relation in $P(X)$ in case ρ satisfies each of the following conditions:

If $A_i \rho B_j$ for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and for any $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, then there exists a set C in $P(X)$ such that $A_i \rho C$ and $C \rho B_j$ for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and any $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

If $A \subseteq B$, then $A \rho^- B$

If $A \rho B$, then $A^\wedge \subseteq B$ and $A \subseteq B^\vee$

The concept of a lower indefinite cut set for a real-valued function was defined by Brooks [2] as follows:

Definition 4. If f is a real-valued function defined on a space X and if $\{x \in X : f(x) < \varphi\} \subseteq A(f, \varphi) \subseteq \{x \in X : f(x) \leq \varphi\}$ for a real number φ , then $A(f, \varphi)$ is called a lower indefinite cut set in the domain of f at the level φ .

Theorem 1. Let g and f be real-valued functions on the topological

space X , in which kernel sets are open, with $g \leq f$. If there exists a strong binary relation ρ on the power set of X and if there exist lower indefinite cut sets $A(f, t)$ and $A(g, t)$ in the domain of f and g at the level t for each rational number t such that if $t_1 < t_2$ then $A(f, t_1) \rho A(g, t_2)$, then there exists a contra-continuous function h defined on X such that $g \leq h \leq f$.

Proof 1. Let g and f be real-valued functions defined on the X such that $g \leq f$. By hypothesis there exists a strong binary relation ρ on the power set of X and there exist lower indefinite cut sets $A(f, t)$ and $A(g, t)$ in the domain of f and g at the level t for each rational number t such that if $t_1 < t_2$ then $A(f, t_1) \rho A(g, t_2)$.

Define functions F and G mapping the rational numbers Q into the power set of X by $F(t) = A(f, t)$ and $G(t) = A(g, t)$. If t_1 and t_2 are any elements of Q with $t_1 < t_2$, then $F(t_1) \rho^- F(t_2)$, $G(t_1) \rho^- G(t_2)$, and $F(t_1) \rho G(t_2)$. By Lemmas 1 and 2 of [16] it follows that there exists a function H mapping Q into the power set of X such that if t_1 and t_2 are any rational numbers with $t_1 < t_2$, then $F(t_1) \rho H(t_2)$, $H(t_1) \rho H(t_2)$ and $H(t_1) \rho G(t_2)$.

For any x in X , let $h(x) = \inf \{t \in Q : x \in H(t)\}$

We first verify that $g \leq h \leq f$. If x is $H(t)$ then x is in $G(t)$ for any $t > h$; since x is in $G(t) = A(g, t)$ implies that $g(x) \leq t$, it follows that $g(x) \leq h$. Hence $g \leq h$. If x is not in $H(t)$, then x is not in $F(t)$ for any $t < h$; since x is not in $F(t) = A(f, t)$ implies that $f(x) > t$, it follows that $f(x) \geq h$. Hence $h \leq f$.

Also, for any rational numbers t_1 and t_2 with $t_1 < t_2$, we have $h^{-1}(t_1, t_2) = H(t_2)^\vee \setminus H(t_1)^\wedge$. Hence $h^{-1}(t_1, t_2)$ is closed in X , i.e., h is a contra-continuous function on X .

The above proof used the technique of theorem 1 in [15].

Theorem 2. Let $P1$ and $P2$ be cc -property and X be a space that satisfies the weak cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$. Also assume that g and f are functions on X such that $g \leq f$, g has property $P1$ and f has property $P2$. The space X has the strong cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$ if and only if there exist lower cut sets $A(f - g, 2^{-n})$ and there exists a sequence $\{H_n\}$ of subsets of X such that (i) for each n , H_n and $A(f - g, 2^{-n})$ are completely separated by contra-continuous functions, and (ii) $\{x \in X : (f - g)(x) > 0\} = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} H_n$.

Proof 2. Theorem 3, of [20].

Theorem 3. Let $P1$ and $P2$ be cc -properties and assume that the space X satisfied the weak cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$. The space X satisfies the strong cc -insertion property for $(P1, P2)$ if and only if X satisfies the strong cc -insertion property for $(P1, cc)$ and for $(cc, P2)$.

Proof 3. Theorem 3, of [20].

Applications 1. Before stating the consequences of theorems 1, 2, we suppose that X is a topological space whose kernel sets are open.

Corollary 1. If for each pair of disjoint α -open (resp. C -open) sets $G1, G2$ of X , there exist closed sets $F1$ and $F2$ of X such that $G1 \subseteq F1$, $G2 \subseteq F2$ and $F1 \cap F2 = \emptyset$ then X has the weak cc -insertion property for $(c\alpha c, c\alpha c)$ (resp. (cCc, cCc)).

Proof 4. Let g and f be real-valued functions defined on X , such that f and g are $c\alpha c$ (resp. cCc), and $g \leq f$. If a binary relation ρ is defined by $A \rho B$ in case $\alpha(A^\wedge) \subseteq \alpha(B^\vee)$ (resp. $C(A^\wedge) \subseteq C(B^\vee)$), then by hypothesis ρ is a strong binary relation in the power set of X . If t_1 and t_2 are any elements of Q with $t_1 < t_2$, then

$$A(f, t_1) \subseteq \{x \in X : f(x) \leq t_1\} \subseteq \{x \in X : g(x) < t_2\} \subseteq A(g, t_2);$$

since $\{x \in X : f(x) \leq t_1\}$ is an α -open (resp. C -open) set and since $\{x \in X : g(x) < t_2\}$ is an α -closed (resp. C -closed) set, it follows that $\alpha(A(f, t_1)^\wedge) \subseteq \alpha(A(g, t_2)^\vee)$ (resp. $C(A(f, t_1)^\wedge) \subseteq C(A(g, t_2)^\vee)$). Hence $t_1 < t_2$ implies that $A(f, t_1) \rho A(g, t_2)$. The proof follows from Theorem 1.

Corollary 2. If for each pair of disjoint α -open (resp. C -open) sets $G1, G2$, there exist closed sets $F1$ and $F2$ such that $G1 \subseteq F1$, $G2 \subseteq F2$ and $F1 \cap F2 = \emptyset$ then every contra α -continuous (resp. contra- C -continuous) function is contra-continuous.

Proof 5. Let f be a real-valued contra- α -continuous (resp. contra- C -continuous) function defined on X . Set $g = f$, then by Corollary 1, there exists a contra continuous function h such that $g = h = f$

Corollary 3. If for each pair of disjoint α -open (resp. C-open) sets G_1, G_2 of X , there exist closed sets F_1 and F_2 of X such that $G_1 \subseteq F_1, G_2 \subseteq F_2$ and $F_1 \cap F_2 = \emptyset$ then X has the strong cc-insertion property for $(c\alpha c, c\alpha c)$ (resp. (cCc, cCc)).

Proof 6. Let g and f be real-valued functions defined on the X , such that f and g are $c\alpha c$ (resp. cCc), and $g \leq f$. Set $h = (f + g)/2$, thus $g \leq h \leq f$ and if $g(x) < f(x)$ for any x in X , then $g(x) < h(x) < f(x)$. Also, by Corollary 2, since g and f are contra-continuous functions hence h is a contra-continuous function.

Corollary 4. If for each pair of disjoint subsets G_1, G_2 of X , such that G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open, there exist closed subsets F_1 and F_2 of X such that $G_1 \subseteq F_1, G_2 \subseteq F_2$ and $F_1 \cap F_2 = \emptyset$ then X have the weak cc-insertion property for $(c\alpha c, cCc)$ and $(cCc, c\alpha c)$.

Proof 7. Let g and f be real-valued functions defined on X , such that g is $c\alpha c$ (resp. cCc) and f is cCc (resp. $c\alpha c$), with $g \leq f$. If a binary relation ρ is defined by $A \rho B$ in case $C(A^\wedge) \subseteq \alpha(B^\vee)$ (resp. $\alpha(A^\wedge) \subseteq C(B^\vee)$), then by hypothesis ρ is a strong binary relation in the power set of X . If t_1 and t_2 are any elements of Q with $t_1 < t_2$, then $A(f, t_1) \subseteq \{x \in X : f(x) \leq t_1\} \subseteq \{x \in X : g(x) < t_2\} \subseteq A(g, t_2)$; since $\{x \in X : f(x) \leq t_1\}$ is a C-open (resp. α -open) set and since $\{x \in X : g(x) < t_2\}$ is an α -closed (resp. C-closed) set, it follows that $C(A(f, t_1)^\wedge) \subseteq \alpha(A(g, t_2)^\vee)$ (resp. $\alpha(A(f, t_1)^\wedge) \subseteq C(A(g, t_2)^\vee)$). Hence $t_1 < t_2$ implies that $A(f, t_1) \rho A(g, t_2)$. The proof follows from Theorem 1. Before stating consequences of Theorem 2, we state and prove the necessary lemmas

Lemma 1. The following conditions on the space X are equivalent: For each pair of disjoint subsets G_1, G_2 of X , such that G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open, there exist closed subsets F_1, F_2 of X such that $G_1 \subseteq F_1, G_2 \subseteq F_2$ and $F_1 \cap F_2 = \emptyset$.

If G is a C-open (resp. α -open) subset of X which is contained in an α -closed (resp. C-closed) subset F of X , then there exists a closed subset H of X such that $G \subseteq H \subseteq H^\wedge \subseteq F$.

Proof 8. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Suppose that $G \subseteq F$, where G and F are C-open (resp. α -open) and α -closed (resp. C-closed) subsets of X , respectively. Hence, F^c is an α -open (resp. C-open) and $G \cap F^c = \emptyset$.

By (i) there exists two disjoint closed subsets F_1, F_2 such that $G \subseteq F_1$ and $F^c \subseteq F_2$. But $F^c \subseteq F_2 \Rightarrow F_2^c \subseteq F$,

And hence

$$F_1 \cap F_2 = \emptyset \Rightarrow F_1 \subseteq F_2^c$$

$$G \subseteq F_1 \subseteq F_2^c \subseteq F$$

And since F_2^c is an open subset containing F_1 , we conclude that $F_1^\wedge \subseteq F_2^c$, i.e.,

$$G \subseteq F_1 \subseteq F_1^\wedge \subseteq F$$

By setting $H = F_1$, condition (ii) holds.

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Suppose that G_1, G_2 are two disjoint subsets of X , such that G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open.

This implies that $G_2 \subseteq G_1^c$ and G_1^c is an α -closed subset of X . Hence by (ii) there exists a closed set H such that $G_2 \subseteq H \subseteq H^\wedge \subseteq G_1^c$.

But

$$H \subseteq H^\wedge \Rightarrow H \cap (H^\wedge)^c = \emptyset$$

and

$$H^\wedge \subseteq G_1^c \Rightarrow G_1 \subseteq (H^\wedge)^c$$

Furthermore, $(H^\wedge)^c$ is a closed subset of X . Hence $G_2 \subseteq H, G_1 \subseteq (H^\wedge)^c$ and $H \cap (H^\wedge)^c = \emptyset$. This means that condition (i) holds.

Lemma 2. Suppose that X is a topological space. If each pair of disjoint subsets G_1, G_2 of X , where G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open, can be separated by closed subsets of X then there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $h(G_2) = 0$ and $h(G_1) = 1$.

Proof 9. Suppose G_1 and G_2 are two disjoint subsets of X , where G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open. Since $G_1 \cap G_2 = \emptyset$, hence $G_2 \subseteq G_1^c$. In particular, since G_1^c is an α -closed subset of X containing the C-open subset G_2 of X , by Lemma 1, there exists a closed subset $H_{1/2}$ such that

$$G_2 \subseteq H_{1/2} \subseteq H_{1/2}^\wedge \subseteq G_1^c$$

Note that $H_{1/2}$ is also an α -closed subset of X and contains G_2 , and G_1^c is an α -closed subset of X and contains the C-open subset $H_{1/2}^\wedge$ of X . Hence, by Lemma 3.1, there exists closed subsets $H_{1/4}$ and $H_{3/4}$ such that

$$G_2 \subseteq H_{1/4} \subseteq H_{1/4}^\wedge \subseteq H_{1/2} \subseteq H_{1/2}^\wedge \subseteq H_{3/4} \subseteq H_{3/4}^\wedge \subseteq G_1^c.$$

By continuing this method for every $t \in D$, where $D \subseteq [0, 1]$ is the set of rational numbers that their denominators are exponents of 2, we obtain closed subsets H_t with the property that if $t_1, t_2 \in D$ and $t_1 < t_2$, then $H_{t_1} \subseteq H_{t_2}$. We define the function h on X by $h(x) = \inf \{t : x \in H_t\}$ for $x \in G_1$ and $h(x) = 1$ for $x \in G_1$.

Note that for every $x \in X$, $0 \leq h(x) \leq 1$, i.e., h maps X into $[0, 1]$. Also, we note that for any $t \in D$, $G_2 \subseteq H_t$; hence $h(G_2) = 0$. Furthermore, by definition, $h(G_1) = 1$. It remains only to prove that h is a contra-continuous function on X . For every $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, we have if $\alpha \leq 0$ then $\{x \in X : h(x) < \alpha\} = \emptyset$ and if $0 < \alpha$ then $\{x \in X : h(x) < \alpha\} = \cup \{H_t : t < \alpha\}$, hence, they are closed subsets of X . Similarly, if $\alpha < 1$ then $\{x \in X : h(x) < \alpha\} = X$ and if $0 \leq \alpha$ then $\{x \in X : h(x) < \alpha\} = \cup \{(H_t^\wedge)^c : t > \alpha\}$ hence, every of them is a closed subset. Consequently h is a contracontinuous function.

Lemma 3. Suppose that X is a topological space. If each pair of disjoint subsets G_1, G_2 of X , where G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open, can separate by closed subsets of X , and G_1 (resp. G_2) is a closed subsets of X , then there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $h^{-1}(0) = G_1$ (resp. $h^{-1}(0) = G_2$) and $h(G_2) = \{1\}$ (resp. $h(G_1) = \{1\}$)

Proof 10. Suppose that G_1 (resp. G_2) is a closed subset of X . By Lemma 2, there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $h(G_1) = \{0\}$ (resp. $h(G_2) = \{0\}$) and $h(X \setminus G_1) = \{1\}$ (resp. $h(X \setminus G_2) = \{1\}$). Hence, $h^{-1}(0) = G_1$ (resp. $h^{-1}(0) = G_2$) and since $G_2 \subseteq X \setminus G_1$ (resp. $G_1 \subseteq X \setminus G_2$), therefore $h(G_2) = \{1\}$ (resp. $h(G_1) = \{1\}$).

Lemma 4. Suppose that X is a topological space such that every two disjoint C-open and α -open subsets of X can be separated by closed subsets of X . The following conditions are equivalent:

- (i) For every two disjoint subsets G_1 and G_2 of X , where G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open, there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $h^{-1}(0) = G_1$ (resp. $h^{-1}(0) = G_2$) and $h^{-1}(1) = G_2$ (resp. $h^{-1}(1) = G_1$).
- (ii) Every α -open (resp. C-open) subset of X is closed subsets of X .
- (iii) Every α -closed (resp. C-closed) subset of X is an open subsets of X .

Proof 11. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Suppose that G is an α -open (resp. C-open) subset of X . Since \emptyset is a C-open (resp. α -open) subset of X , by (i) there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $h^{-1}(0) = G$. Set

$$F_n = \left\{x \in X : h(x) < \frac{1}{n}\right\} \text{ Then for every } n \in \mathbb{N}, F_n \text{ is a closed subset of } X \text{ and } \bigcap_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n = \{x \in X : h(x) = 0\} = G.$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (i) Suppose that G_1 and G_2 are two disjoint subsets of X , where G_1 is α -open and G_2 is C-open. By Lemma 3, there exists a contra-continuous function $f : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $f^{-1}(0) = G_1$ and $f(G_2) = \{1\}$.

Set $G = \left\{x \in X : f(x) < \frac{1}{2}\right\}$, $F = \left\{x \in X : f(x) = \frac{1}{2}\right\}$, and $H = \left\{x \in X : f(x) > \frac{1}{2}\right\}$. Then $G \cup F$ and $H \cup F$ are two open subsets of X and $(G \cup F) \cap (H \cup F) = \emptyset$. By Lemma 3, there exists a contra-continuous function $g : X \rightarrow \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$ Such that, $g^{-1}(1) = G_2$ and $g(G \cup F) = \left\{\frac{1}{2}\right\}$.

Define h by $h(x) = f(x)$ for $x \in G \cup F$, and $h(x) = g(x)$ for $x \in H \cup F$. Then h is well-defined and a contra-continuous function, since $(G \cup F) \cap (H \cup F) = \emptyset$ and for every $x \in F$ we have $f(x) = g(x) = \frac{1}{2}$. Furthermore, $(G \cup F) \cup (H \cup F) = X$, hence h defined on X and maps to $[0, 1]$. Also, we have $h^{-1}(0) = G_1$ and $h^{-1}(1) = G_2$

(ii) \Leftrightarrow

(iii) By De Morgan law and noting that the complement of every open subset of X is a closed subset of X and complement of every closed subset of X is an open subset of X , the equivalence is hold.

Corollary 5. If for every two disjoint subsets G_1 and G_2 of X , where G_1 is α -open (resp. C-open) and G_2 is C-open (resp. α -open), there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that, $h^{-1}(0) =$

G_1 and $h^{-1}(1) = G_2$ then X has the strong cc -insertion property for $(c\alpha c, cCc)$ (resp. $(cCc, c\alpha c)$).

Proof 12. Since for every two disjoint subsets G_1 and G_2 of X , where G_1 is α -open (resp. C -open) and G_2 is C -open (resp. α -open), there exists a contra-continuous function $h : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that, $h^{-1}(0) = G_1$ and $h^{-1}(1) = G_2$, define $F_1 = \left\{x \in X : h(x) < \frac{1}{2}\right\}$ and $F_2 = \left\{x \in X : h(x) > \frac{1}{2}\right\}$.

Then F_1 and F_2 are two disjoint closed subsets of X that contain G_1 and G_2 , respectively. Hence by Corollary 4, X has the weak cc -insertion property for $(c\alpha c, cCc)$ and $(cCc, c\alpha c)$. Now, assume that g and f are functions on X such that $g \leq f$, g is $c\alpha c$ (resp. cCc) and f is cc . Since $f - g$ is $c\alpha c$ (resp. cCc), therefore the lower cut set $A(f - g, 2^{-n}) = \{x \in X : (f - g)(x) \leq 2^{-n}\}$ is an α -open (resp. C -open) subset of X . Now setting $H_n = \{x \in X : (f - g)(x) > 2^{-n}\}$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then by Lemma 4, H_n is an open subset of X and we have $\{x \in X : (f - g)(x) > 0\} = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} H_n$ and for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, H_n and $A(f - g, 2^{-n})$ are disjoint subsets of X . By Lemma 2, H_n and $A(f - g, 2^{-n})$ can be completely separated by contra-continuous functions. Hence by Theorem 2, X has the strong cc -insertion property for $(c\alpha c, cc)$ (resp. (cCc, cc)).

By an analogous argument, we can prove that X has the strong cc -insertion property for (cc, cCc) (resp. $(cc, c\alpha c)$). Hence, by Theorem 3, X has the strong cc -insertion property for $(c\alpha c, cCc)$ (resp. $(cCc, c\alpha c)$).

Acknowledgements

This research was partially supported by Centre of Excellence for Mathematics (University of Isfahan).

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